

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of glutathione (reduced) (γ -L-glutamyl-L-cysteinylglycine) by pyridinium chlorochromate in acid medium

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Abstract : The electron transfer reaction between glutathione (reduced) (GSH) and pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC) has been studied spectrophotometrically over the range $3.00 \leq 10^3[\text{GSH}] \leq 6.00 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $0.01 \leq [\text{H}^+] \leq 0.03 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $293 \leq T \leq 313 \text{ K}$. The rate of reaction is found to increase with the increase in $[\text{GSH}]_T$ and $[\text{H}^+]_T$. The reaction is found to exhibit first order dependence in $[\text{GSH}]_T$, $[\text{H}^+]_T$ and $[\text{PCC}]_T$. The ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1}) and ΔS^\ddagger ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) for the electron transfer reaction are found to be 5.90 and -177.00. The product of the reaction was found to be GSSG [((2S)-2-amino-5-(((2R)-3-((2R)-2-(((4S)-4-amino-5-hydroxy-5-oxopentanoyl)amino)-3-(carboxymethylamino)-3-oxopropyl)disulfanyl-1-(carboxymethylamino)-1-oxopropan-2-yl)amino)-5-oxopentanoic acid)].

Keywords : Pyridinium chlorochromate, glutathione (reduced), electron transfer reaction.

Introduction

The electron transfer reactions of PCC with various molecules have been studied¹⁻¹². PCC is a mild oxidizing agent. The compound has been used extensively for the study of redox reactions of many biomolecules, but the electron transfer reaction of PCC with peptide GSH has not been studied. However the redox reactions of [GSH] with other oxidant have been studied¹³⁻¹⁶. The tripeptide GSH is the major low molecular mass thiol compound in plants and animals and its peptide γ -linkage is thought to protect it from degradation by aminopeptidases. It plays an important role in signal transduction, gene expression, apoptosis, protein glutathionylation and NO metabolism.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Pyridinium chlorochromate has been synthesized by following the reported method^{17,18}. The compound was characterized by estimating Cr^{VI} iodometrically¹⁹. All other chemicals used were of analR grade. Doubly distilled water was used to prepare all the solutions. The acid strength of the medium was maintained by addition of HClO_4 . Kinetic measurements were recorded on a SYSTRONICS 119 PC scanning UV-Vis spectropho-

meter. Reaction progress was monitored at 435 nm (Fig. 1). Pseudo-first order condition were maintained through out the runs by using a large excess (> 5 fold) of [GSH]. The k_{obs} values were obtained from the slope of $-\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ versus 't' plots.

$$-\ln(A_t - A_\infty) = k_{\text{obs}} t - C$$

where A_t and A_∞ are the absorbances of the reaction mixture at time 't' and at the completion of the reaction. The reported rate data represented as an average of duplicate runs were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. The correlation coefficient of the plots used to determine k_{obs} were found to be 0.99 in most of the cases.

Stoichiometry :

The stoichiometry of the reaction was studied at 303 K where $[\text{PCC}]_T$ was kept constant at $4.00 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[\text{GSH}] = 6.00 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. From the decrease in $[\text{PCC}]_T$ and $[\text{GSH}]_T$ the stoichiometry of the reaction can be written as

Results

The kinetic results obtained for the above reaction may be summarized as follows. With the varying concentration of $10^3[\text{GSH}]_T$ in the range 3.00 to 6.00 mol dm^{-3} , the $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1}) (298 K) increased from 5.18 to

Fig. 1. Repetitive spectral scan of PCC with GSH. (2) $[PCC] = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (1) $[GSH] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H^+] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $T = 303 \text{ K}$, at different time intervals of 2 min (Curve 3-10), Curve 11 is after 24 h.

12.78 when $[H^+]_T = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[PCC]_T = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Table 1). The $[GSH]_T/[PCC]_T$ was varied from 7.50 to 15.00. The k_{obs} versus $[GSH]_T$ plot (Fig. 2) was linear at all reported $[H^+]_T$ indicating first order dependence of the reaction on $[GSH]_T$. Furthermore, the second order rate constant k_2 (298 K) = $k_{\text{obs}}/[GSH]_T$ almost remain constant. $k_2 = (0.19 \pm 0.02) \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ indicating the fact that overall order of the reaction is two. As the order of the reaction is one with respect to $[GSH]_T$, the order of the reaction is one with respect to $[PCC]_T$. The rate law is therefore given by eq. (2).

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [PCC]_T \quad (2)$$

With $[PCC]_T = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[GSH]_T = 3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (298 K) changed from 5.18 to 16.64 s^{-1} as $[H^+]_T$ was changed from 0.01 to 0.03 mol dm^{-3} . This behavior was repeated for the entire $[GSH]_T$ range 0.003 to 0.006 mol dm^{-3} . By increasing $[H^+]$ the value of k_{obs} increased (Fig. 3).

The temperature variation was carried out in the range 293 to 313 K. With the increase in temperature, k_{obs} was found to increase. With $[GSH]_T = 3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[PCC]_T = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H^+] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1}) changed from 4.28 to 9.30 as the temperature was changed from 293 to 313 K (Table 1).

The activation parameters were determined from the composite rate constants using Eyring equation. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were found to be 5.9 kJ mol^{-1} and $-177.0 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The negative values of activation parameters favour the formation of the ordered transition state.

Discussion

Since pK_1 , pK_2 , pK_3 and pK_4 of GSH are 2.05, 3.47, 8.63 and 9.52 (Scheme 1), at higher concentration of the acid 0.03 mol dm^{-3} , the undissociated form of GSH will participate in the electron transfer reaction. The reaction sequence delineated below (Scheme 2) is consistent with

Since,

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{PCC}]_{\text{T}} \quad (14)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{GSH}]_{\text{e}} [\text{H}^+]_{\text{e}}}{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+]_{\text{e}}} \quad (15)$$

$[\text{GSH}]_{\text{e}}$ and $[\text{H}^+]_{\text{e}}$ can be replaced by $[\text{GSH}]_{\text{T}}$ and $[\text{H}^+]_{\text{T}}$ because the concentration of $[\text{GSH}]_{\text{T}}$ and $[\text{H}^+]_{\text{T}}$ is much higher than the concentration of $[\text{PCC}]_{\text{T}}$, hence eq. (15) can be written as eq. (16).

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{GSH}]_{\text{T}} [\text{H}^+]_{\text{T}}}{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+]_{\text{T}}} \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{k_{\text{obs}}}{[\text{GSH}]} = k_2 = \frac{k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+]_{\text{T}}}{1 + K_1 [\text{H}^+]_{\text{T}}} \quad (17)$$

k_2 is the second order rate constant for the electron transfer reaction.

Eq. (16) can be changed to eq. (18)

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k_1 K_2 [\text{GSH}]_{\text{T}}} + \frac{1}{k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{GSH}]_{\text{T}} [\text{H}^+]_{\text{T}}} \quad (18)$$

The plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{H}^+]_{\text{T}}^{-1}$ should be linear for every $[\text{GSH}]_{\text{T}}$ changing from 3.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ to 6.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ (Fig. 4). The slope of this plot is $1/k_1 K_1 K_2 [\text{GSH}]_{\text{T}}$ and intercept is $1/k_1 K_2 [\text{GSH}]_{\text{T}}$. The slope for each $[\text{H}^+]_{\text{T}}$ was plotted against $[\text{GSH}]_{\text{T}}^{-1}$. The plots were found to be linear. The slope of the plot will be equal to $1/(k_1 K_1 K_2)$, the values of $k_1 K_1 K_2$ will be equal to reciprocal of the new slope. The values of $k_1 K_1 K_2$ were determined for four different temperatures rang-

Fig. 2. The plots of $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1}) versus $[\text{GSH}]_{\text{T}}$ (mol dm^{-3}) at different $[\text{H}^+]$. $[\text{PCC}]_{\text{T}} = 4.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³, $T = 298$ K. $[\text{H}^+]$ was varied from 0.01 to 0.03 mol dm⁻³ and $[\text{GSH}]$ was varied from 0.003 to 0.006 mol dm⁻³.

Table 1

Temp. (K)	$10^3 [\text{GSH}]_{\text{T}}$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1})				
		$[\text{H}^+]$ (mol dm ⁻³)				
		0.010	0.015	0.020	0.025	0.030
293	3.0	4.28	7.04	9.84	12.74	15.74
298	3.0	5.18	7.94	10.74	13.64	16.64
303	3.0	6.42	9.18	11.98	14.88	17.88
308	3.0	7.67	10.43	13.23	16.13	19.13
313	3.0	9.30	12.06	14.86	17.76	20.76
293	4.0	6.41	9.17	11.97	14.87	17.87
298	4.0	7.31	10.07	12.87	15.77	18.77
303	4.0	8.55	11.31	14.11	17.01	20.01
308	4.0	9.80	12.56	15.36	18.26	21.26
313	4.0	11.43	14.19	16.99	19.89	22.89
293	5.0	8.66	11.42	14.22	17.12	20.12
298	5.0	9.56	12.32	15.12	18.02	21.02
303	5.0	10.80	13.52	16.36	19.26	22.26
308	5.0	12.05	14.81	17.61	20.51	23.51
313	5.0	13.68	16.44	19.24	22.14	25.14
293	6.0	11.88	14.64	17.44	20.34	23.34
298	6.0	12.78	15.54	18.34	21.24	24.24
303	6.0	14.02	16.78	19.58	22.48	25.48
308	6.0	15.27	18.03	20.83	23.73	26.73
313	6.0	16.90	19.66	22.46	25.36	28.36

Fig. 3. The plots of $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1}) versus $[\text{H}^+]$ (mol dm^{-3}) at different $[\text{GSH}]_{\text{T}}$. $[\text{PCC}]_{\text{T}} = 4.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³, $T = 298$ K. $[\text{H}^+]$ was varied from 0.01 to 0.03 mol dm⁻³ and $[\text{GSH}]$ was varied from 0.003 to 0.006 mol dm⁻³.

ing from 293 to 313 K. The activation parameters were determined from the composite rate constants using Eyring equation. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were found to be 5.9 kJ mol⁻¹ and -177.0 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹. The negative values of activation parameters favour the formation of the ordered transition state.

Characterization of product :

The FTIR spectra of GSH (Fig. 5) and the GSSG

Fig. 4. The plots of $10^4 k_{\text{obs}}^-1$ (s) versus $[H^+]$ ($\text{mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3$) at different $[GSH]_T$. $[PCC]_T = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $T = 298 \text{ K}$. $[H^+]$ was varied from 0.01 to 0.03 mol dm^{-3} and $[GSH]$ was varied from 0.003 to 0.006 mol dm^{-3} .

Fig. 5. IR spectra of pure GSH.

(Fig. 6) [(2*S*)-2-amino-5-[[*(2R)*]-3-[[*(2R)*]-2-[[*(4S)*]-4-amino-5-hydroxy-5-oxopentanoyl]amino]-3-(carboxymethylamino)-3-oxopropyl]disulfanyl-1-(carboxymethylamino)-1-oxopropan-2-yl]amino]-5-oxopentanoic acid] were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer (UK) FTIR spectrophotometer. A broad peak at 3419 cm^{-1} in the product may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{N-H}} (\text{NH}_3^+)$, as compared to 3252 cm^{-1} and 3026 cm^{-1} in GSH. The shifting to higher frequency is probably due to an association of water molecules with the product. The NH_3^+ bending bands and a strong absorption peak of carboxylate ion are mixed up and a broad band is observed at 1636 cm^{-1} in the product compared

to 1600 cm^{-1} , 1538 cm^{-1} and 1395 cm^{-1} peaks in GSH. The weak band at 2526 cm^{-1} in GSH due to S-H stretching is absent in the product suggesting the dimerisation of GSH having S-S linkage. Strong and broad peak of 1089 cm^{-1} and a sharp peak of 628 cm^{-1} in the product corresponds to 1073 cm^{-1} and 691 cm^{-1} in GSH is due to the free NH_2 twisting and rocking²⁰. The structure of GSSG is mentioned in Fig. 7.

Conclusion :

GSH, a tripeptide (γ -L-glutamyl-L-cysteinylglycine), is the major low molecular mass thiol compound in plants and animals²¹ and its peptidic γ -linkage is thought to pro-

Fig. 6. IR spectra of the product (GSSG).

Fig. 7. Structure of GSSG.

tect it from degradation by aminopeptidases. Its role in the electron transfer reaction is of biological interest. Oxidation of GSH under physiological condition is taking place producing GSSG. During the reaction between PCC and GSH, the products of the reaction are found to be Cr^{III} and GSSG. Using PCC, therefore estimation of GSH in aqueous medium is possible.

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